

Lookism as a Gender-Specific Concern: Assessment of Male and Female Attitudes towards Appearance of TV Programme Presenters in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined male and female TV viewers' attitudes towards appearance of TV programme presenters in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria, in order to find out if lookism is a gender-specific concern. The work generally assessed whether female TV viewers in Owerri are more obsessed than men about appearances of TV presenters and to know which gender suffers lookism the most in TV presentation. The study was anchored on the lookism theory. The cluster and systematic sampling techniques were adopted and 364 male and female TV viewers in Owerri were sampled from 126,377 residents. The study finds, among others, that attraction to appearance is a trait shared by male and female TV viewers in Owerri but female viewers are more concerned about the manifest observable physical features of the TV presenters like their clothing and hair style than the men; and women are mostly the *victims* of lookism in the broadcast media. The study recommended that TV producers should ensure they keep the hairdo, clothing and make-up of the female presenters as moderate as possible to avoid warranting undue attention on the presenters.

Keywords: Lookism, gender, concern, TV, presenters.

Suggested Citation: Fab-Ukozor, N. & Ejem, A. A. (2016). Lookism as a Gender-Specific Concern: Assessment of Male and Female Attitudes towards Appearance of TV Programme Presenters in Owerri, Imo State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Leadership, Education and Business Studies*, 1(1), 39-54

Introduction

There is always a tendency for audience members to develop some sort of preference for a particular broadcast programme, broadcast channel or broadcast presenter over others. Several studies have been conducted addressing numerous questions about these media preferences and channel preferences (Nigatu, 2014; Ray-Udeajah, 2012; Onah and Anyanwu, 1989; etc.). Most of those studies have focused on the inherent social structures of the audience, that is: their demographic and psychographic compositions; and sometimes attention is paid on the media structure.

Audience members, men and women, of all mass media messages are demographically, emotionally, psychologically, culturally and intellectually different. That is why Folarin (1998, p.59) says that “it has become increasingly clear that individuals differ in their personal psychological organizations; people pay attention to media messages and interpret them in line with their interests, belief, values and experiences. These determine the preferences for a particular television programme to another.” According to Becker (2003), the most reliable findings from all the research in media relationship is the fact that individuals vary tremendously to the degree to which they use the media. These discrepancies influence the preference they give to one media offering over another, and their preferences determine the extent of exposure they give to, say, television programmes and/or television channels; or how they perceive such message, retain and recall them when the need arises.

Konkwo (1997, p. 49) was more detailed in listing the factors that affect media preference among the audience. He stressed how media preference is determined by several factors such as location, age, sex, educational qualification, economic status, and mental situation of the audience as well as their tastes, motivation, moods, beliefs, outlook, values, norms, aversion, interests, belief, values and experiences. The audience is, without doubt, also beauty sensitive. Appearance appeals to him.

That is where lookism comes in. Lookism is mentioned largely because we are living in a world where appearance is an important factor in human and material evaluation. Lookism is an instinctive behaviour in almost every human, and it is expressed in varying degrees in humans. Lookism generally means the undeniable human instincts to prefer what is more beautiful. Lookism, according to O’Brien (2008), is a term used to refer to the positive stereotypes, prejudice, and preferential treatment given to physically attractive people, or more generally to people whose appearance matches cultural preferences. It means, paying more attention to appearance at the expense of substance and other valuable characteristics.

Alluding to the lookism concept, Jin (2004) says that many TV programmes show us only those who have pretty faces and good body shapes. However, we rarely see those who are fat and ugly except comedians in TV shows. It connotes that ordinary people should have pretty faces and good body shapes. Since Television programmes are presented by humans who are seen by the audience, and the audience is made up of human beings whose instinctive behaviours are usually guided by appearance, like we have cited earlier, then is there the natural instinct among the

broadcast audience to prefer what is more beautiful and graceful? While this relationship has been suggested by Fox (2014), and Miller, Lurye, Zosuls and Ruble (2009) among other researchers, there is an interesting issue that raises more questions, especially among gender scholars.

While lookism generally assumes that appearances are considered more central to the definition of an individual, Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) suggested that lookism is a gender-specific concern when they explained that females learn to be more concerned with observable body attributes rather than focusing on non-observable body attributes, and men are the opposite. Females, more than men, are more defined by appearance, and they too have accepted and internalized their 'objectification' and have become obsessively conscious of observable physical appearance and pay less attention to non-observable body attributes. This assertion requires empirical evidence.

Against this backdrop therefore, this work strives to determine if lookism on TV is a gender-specific concern. That means, to know whether men or women are particularly victims of lookism or are particularly obsessed with lookism. It basically assesses male and female attitudes towards appearance of broadcast programme presenters in Owerri.

The Problem

The lookism theory is already a *bold* proposition because it assumes that appearances are considered more central to the definition of an individual. It is even more audacious when Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) asserted that women are mostly victims of lookism because of the proclivity for people to describe them in terms of what they look like and boys in terms of what they do. Others, such as Fox (1997) think women themselves are even guilty for their obsession with appearance. But as Daubney (2015, p. 2) said, it is "no longer clear who is a victim of appearance stereotypes and who is obsessional with appearance," as men are now beginning to be boxed into more appearance pigeon-holes than women in the media. Daubney's (2015) assertion is a complete departure from conventional wisdom, and it has sparked off debates as to who, if any, is a specific victim of lookism in the media.

Television has often come into the discussion of lookism because TV programmes tend to show us only those who have pretty faces and good body shapes. There is therefore the need gauge who really is a victim of lookism in the media using the TV experience. That is to say, are female TV viewers in Owerri more obsessed than men to observable body attributes rather than focusing on non-observable body attributes of presenters or the substance of the TV presentation, and are female presenters the ones who are mostly defined by appearances?

This study therefore had the following objectives:

- 1) To determine if male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of TV presenters.
- 2) To examine what physical features about the TV presenters that male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe.

- 3) To examine the attitudes of male and female TV viewers in Owerri towards the physical features of the TV presenters.
- 4) To ascertain whether male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of female TV presenters more than male TV presenters.
- 5) To determine if male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to pay more attention to the appearances of TV presenters than their presentations.

Research Questions

This study was guided by the following research questions:

- 1) Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of TV presenters?
- 2) What physical features about the TV presenters do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe?
- 3) What are the attitudes of male and female TV viewers in Owerri towards the physical features of the TV presenters?
- 4) Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of female TV presenters more than male TV presenters?
- 5) Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to pay more attention to the appearances of TV presenters than their presentations?

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Theoretical foundation

This study is anchored on the lookism theory. The theory of lookism was introduced by Dunn (1991). Lookism theory assumes that many people make automatic judgments of others based on their physical appearance, and that influence how they respond to those people. Lookism is used to refer to the positive stereotypes, prejudice and preferential treatment given to physically attractive people, or more generally to people whose appearance matches cultural preference.

Lookism places undue value on physical appearances. Etcoff (1999) explains the lookism theory when he says that we face a world where lookism is one of the most pervasive but denied prejudices. Adrian (2014) says that physically attractive people have advantage at work; they are more likely to be selected for jobs.

No mass media can potentially project lookism tendencies more than TV because viewers can see their presenters. There is a tendency that attractive presenters on TV are perceived to be more socially appealing, professionally adept, intellectually competent and emotionally adjusted.

Television Programmes and their Presentations

Television programmes are produced using such professionals as producers, directors, presenters, talents and musicians with the ripple effect of educating, informing, entertaining and creating awareness as its main purposes and objectives.

Hillard (2010, p. 2) explains that a programme is a “broadcast material created to meet certain specific needs or affirm some set objectives and transmitted to some predetermined target audience, which involves the task of choosing messages and scheduling them in meaningful.” Programme is the main menu of broadcasting. That is why Eastman (1993) called it, the bedrock and mainstay of broadcasting. It is a strategic production and transmission of broadcast message appropriate or suitable to a particular segment of pre-defined target audience.

In the creation of Television programme, according to Hillard (2010), certain factors are to be considered, namely: facts about the audience, such as size, literacy, religion, occupation, language, culture, political orientations, etc; time of day and day of week the programme will be on broadcast, the particular item of interest and length of the programme. TV programmes can come in various formats.

Whatever format, a programme needs a presenter and an audience: a presenter who can explain what is happening and guide the listener through the subject(s) being discussed. The presenter is crucial to the success of the programme. Then, without the interest and attention of an audience, a television programme producer or presenter cannot achieve his set object. The challenge is not only to make audience want to watch or listen but to also help them understand, remember and act on the information or ideas that the presenter shares.

There are things presenters do and techniques they adopt and apply to get the audience to be exposed to their programmes. These techniques: humour; posture and body movement; repetition; alliteration; personal experience; story telling; branding the presentation; being brief and concise; smile; good command of English; are the basis that push the audience to prefer watching a particular television programmes over another. Now we consider how the personality and looks of the presenter can also achieve that.

The Television Audience

According to Littlejohn (2011, p. 3), the audience is the singular most important element in mass communication. Every broadcast programme is targeted at a given audience. It is the audience that determines the language, characterization and approach to broadcast programmes. It is also the target audience that determines the artistic condiments and creative elements required to ensure the achievement of programme objective.

A Television programme is a material created to meet certain specific needs or attain some set objectives and transmitted to some predetermined target audience (Owuamalam, 2007). Therefore, the audience is an element of broadcasting that can hardly be overlooked or underestimated.

Nevertheless, while different audience members in different locations receive the broadcast programme simultaneously, the different groups of audience differ in their attitude to and preference for the broadcast programme. That is why some scholars have maintained that the audience of mass communication must be looked at in terms of categories, sub groups or target groups and not as a sheer totality of the population. These audience members are demographically, emotionally, psychologically, culturally and intellectually different. The audience members pay attention to media messages and interpret them in line with their interests, belief, values and experiences. These determine the preferences for a particular television programme to another. They vary tremendously to the degree to which they use the media.

Konkwo (1997, p. 49) said that media preference of the audience is determined by their location, age, sex, educational qualification, economic status, mental situation, tastes, motivation, moods, beliefs, outlook, values, norms, aversion, interests, belief, values and experiences..

Due to inherent factors in audience characteristics, their mass media consumption is subjective and selective. One notable factor that determines audience consumption of the mass media is what Urban (2000, p.7) calls, the three general clusters of demographic, psychographic factors and predispositions. They are called prediction of media use. Media use is often associated with age, sex, income, education, occupation, participation in local social and political affairs, knowledge of socio-political event in the country, community ties sense of community, social class and stratification. All these give the individual wide range of media preference.

Berlose (2006, p.28) notes that the social character of an individual may possibly affect exposure to a medium. Differences in preference for different types of content in the media can be attributed to the individual's mental set which is shaped by both psychological and demographic elements. Other factors that affect media preference are perceptions of modernity, creativity and social expectations.

Emenyonu (1998) cited in Ekanem (2006, p. 39) broadly classified them into demographic and psychographic factors. While the psychographic factors are interests, nature of content and habit; the demographic factors are age, education, income, occupation, and social status.

Ekanem (2006) further reports that a third factor called environmental factor has been identified. This, he says includes availability of the media and preferred contents, time, knowledge of usage of the medium, the viewers' environment and scheduling pattern of some media contents and usage of other media. However, these various classifications strengthen the fact that demographic factors play major roles in media exposure.

Mass media exposure refers to the act of reading, watching or listening to the mass media (Nwabueze 2014, p. 62). Exposure is a major factor for determining the reach and effectiveness of any mass medium in targeting a specific audience group. It is important to say that while exposure is the conscious effort to access and consume the content of a medium, level of exposure refers to the amount of time spent on reading, watching or listening to a medium; so level of exposure is a stronger indicator of media effectiveness than exposure.

Whatever be the case, audience exposure to the mass media is determined by diverse factors.

The Lookism Concept

Lookism is prejudice toward people because of their appearance. It has been receiving increasing attention in media studies and beyond. People we find attractive are given more attention and sometimes preferential treatment and people we find unattractive are denied opportunities. Lookism is to make automatic judgments of others based on their physical appearance.

The term lookism is used to refer to the positive stereotypes, prejudice and preferential treatment given to physically attractive people, or more generally to people whose appearance matches cultural preference. Physical attractiveness is associated with good things while physical unattractiveness is associated with negative things (Etcoff, 1999).

Lookism is a universal concept, and always a concern when it goes beyond the modest desire for beauty and aesthetic appeal. Etcoff (1999, p. 24) notes that “beauty is a universal part of human experience, and that it provokes pleasure, rivets attention, and impels actions that help ensure the survival of our genes. Our extreme sensitivity to beauty is hard-wired, that is, governed by circuits in the brain shaped by natural selection. We love to look at smooth skin, thick shiny hair, curved waists, and symmetrical bodies because in the course of evolution the people who noticed these signals and desired their possessors had more reproductive success.”

Lookism is a pervasive concept. It is felt everywhere. New visual media and technologies, infotainment, virtual reality, corporate image-projection, video games, internet voyeurism and many other developments all in their own ways reinforce the importance of appearances in things and attractiveness in persons. Even in unlikely institutions such as the church and the university, they are scrambling to adapt to unprecedented visual receptivity.

Lookism has crept into the labour market. Hamermesh and Biddle (1994, p. 1186) wrote that “according to recent labor-market research, attractiveness receives a premium and unattractiveness receives a penalty,” and Howse (1998) understood that good looking workers who interact with the company’s clients get paid more year after year, and that fact is reinforced when those good-looking workers inspire others and also increase their productivity. Physically attractive people have advantage at work; they are more likely to be selected for jobs.

The media workers are not left out in lookism. This is mostly projected by Television and magazines. It is obvious that attractive presenters in TV are perceived to be more intellectually competent, emotionally adjusted and socially appealing.

RESEACH DESIGN

This study employed the descriptive survey research design. A sample of male and female TV viewers in Owerri were studied. This was to determine their attitudes towards the appearance of male and female TV presenters in the two TV stations in Owerri, namely NTA Owerri and Orient TV Owerri.

Population

While the population of TV viewers has not been exactly determined, there are 126,377 residents in Owerri Municipal all of whom are potential TV viewers.

Sample Size

The sample size used in this study was 369 respondents. The researchers used the Topman's formula to determine the sample size. The basis for using the Topman formula is that the exact population of TV viewers in the Municipal is not known.

$$\text{Topman's Formula: } n = \frac{Z^2 pq}{e^2}$$

Where n= sample size to be determined

Z= degree of confidence on the Z-score table

p= positive responses

q= negatives responses

e=margin of tolerable error

Applying the details from our pilot study, the following values are substituted in the formula:

Z= 90% on the Z-score table = 1.96

p= 62 or 62% or 0.62 or 0.6

q= 38 or 38% or 0.38 or 0.4

e=5% or 0.05

$$\text{Thus } n = \frac{(1.96)^2 \times 0.6 \times 0.4}{(0.05)^2}$$

$$n = \frac{3.84 \times 0.6 \times 0.4}{0.0025} = \frac{0.9216}{0.0025}$$

$$n = 369$$

Sampling Technique

The cluster and systematic sampling techniques were adopted for this study. First, Owerri municipal was clustered into the 64 major roads that make up the municipal. Then, the researchers wrote out the names of all 64 major roads that make up the municipal, folded them and randomly selected six (10%) streets from the sampling frame. Next was identification of

streets and systematic distribution of the questionnaire at the skip interval of 2 houses (in those streets that did not exceed 125 houses) and 3 houses (for the streets that had up to 200 houses).

Test of Reliability

Before starting analysis, the normality and reliability of the data was checked. The Cronbach's alpha was run using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS). The data was normally distributed and reliability of overall instrument is Cronbach's alpha 0.770, which is above the standard value proposed by Nummally (1978) of 0.70, showing that the research instrument is reliable; which means that the researchers can interpret the results with confidence.

ANALYSIS OF SURVEY DATA

Table 1: Male and Female TV Viewers' Observation of Presenters' Appearances

Options	Male(n)	%	Female(n)	%	Total
Yes	108	66.3	124	65	232
No	34	20.8	20	10.4	54
Not sure	21	12.9	47	24.6	68
Total	163	100	191	100	354

Three hundred and fifty four (354) out of 369 copies of the instrument were returned valid; 163 (46%) of which were males and 191 (54%) were females. Table 1 shows that among the 163 male respondents, 66.3%(108) observe the appearance of TV presenters, 20.8%(34) don't and 12.9%(21) are not sure if they observe the appearance of TV presenters.

Of the female TV viewers, 65%(124) observe the appearance of TV presenters, 10.4%(20) don't and 24.6%(47) are not sure if they observe the appearance of TV presenters.

Table 2: TV Presenters' Physical Features Observed by Male and Female TV Viewers

Options	Male(n)	%	Female(n)	%	Total
Facial Appearance	16	9.9	51	26.8	67
Fashion	32	19.6	86	45	118
Mannerism	69	42.3	22	11.5	91
Not sure	12	7.4	12	6.3	24
Never	34	20.8	20	10.4	54
Total	163	100	191	100	354

Table 2 shows that among the 163 male respondents, 9.9%(16) observe the facial appearance of the TV presenters, 19.6%(32) observe their fashion (clothing, hairdo and make-up), 42.3%(69) observe their mannerism, 7.4%(12) are not sure what they observe, and 20.8%(34) insist they don't observe the appearance of TV presenters.

Among the 191 female respondents, 26.8%(51) observe the facial appearance of the TV presenters, 45%(86) observe their fashion (clothing, hairdo and make-up), 11.5%(22) observe their mannerism, 6.3%(12) are not sure what they observe, and 10.4%(20) insist they don't observe the appearance of TV presenters.

Table 3: Attitudes of Male and Female TV Viewers in Owerri towards the Physical Features of the TV Presenters

Options	Male(n)	%	Female(n)	%	Total
Admiring	34	20.8	90	47.1	66.6
Indifferent	41	25.2	30	15.7	11.2
Critical	52	31.9	48	25.1	22.2
Can't Say	36	22.1	23	12.1	59
Total	163	100	191	100	354

Table 3 shows that among the 163 male respondents, 20.8%(34) express admiration towards appearance of the TV presenters, 25.2%(41) are indifferent about the appearances, 31.9%(52) are critical of the appearances, and 22.1%(36) could not say how they perceive the appearance of TV presenters.

As for the 191 female respondents, 47.1%(90) express admiration towards appearance of the TV presenters, 15.7%(30) are indifferent about the appearances, 25.1%(48) are critical of the appearances, and 12.1%(23) could not say how they perceive the appearance of TV presenters.

Table 4: Proclivity to Observe the Appearances of Female TV Presenters more than Male TV Presenters

Options	Male(n)	%	Female(n)	%	Total
Yes	108	66.3	135	70.7	243
No	21	12.9	34	17.8	55
Can't Say	34	20.8	22	11.5	56
Total	163	100	Total	191	354

Table 4 shows that among the 163 male respondents, 66.3%(108) observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters, for 12.9%(21), the reverse is the case as they observe more male presenters than female presenters and 20.8%(34) could not say if they observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters.

Whereas, among the 191 female respondents, 70.7%(135) observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters, for 17.8%(34), the reverse is the case as they

observe more male presenters than female presenters and 11.5%(22) could not say if they observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters.

Table 5: Proclivity to Observe the Appearances of TV Presenters more than their Presentations

Options	Male(n)	%	Female(n)	%	Total
Yes, all the time	2	1.2	15	7.9	17
Yes, but sometimes	28	17.2	57	29.8	85
No, not at all	121	74.2	96	50.3	217
Can't Say	12	7.4	23	12	35
Total	163	100	191	100	354

Table 5 shows that among the 163 male respondents, 1.2%(2) have a recurring tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, 17.2%(28) have an occasional tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, 74.2%(121) have no tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, and 7.4%(12) could not say no if there is any tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations.

As for the 191 female respondents, 7.9%(15) have a recurring tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, 29.8%(57) have an occasional tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, 50.3%(96) have no tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations, and 12%(23) could not say no if there is any tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The researchers were guided by the research objectives, findings from other studies and the theoretical framework to discuss the findings of this study.

RQ One: Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of TV presenters?

The findings in Table 1 show that 66.3 percent of the male TV viewers observe the appearances of TV presenters and 20.8 percent do not observe the appearances of TV presenters; and 65 percent of the female TV viewers observe the appearances of TV presenters, and only 10.4 percent don't do not observe the appearances of TV presenters. With 66.3 percent of the male TV viewers and 65 percent of the female TV viewers taking note of the appearances of TV presenters, it is equally poised. It shows that gender is not at a factor in determining who takes note of the appearances of the TV presenters, as both men and women seem to always get attracted by appearance.

This is exactly what Etoff (1999, p. 24) means when she said that “lookism is an instinctive behaviour in almost every human, and it is expressed in varying degrees in human...beauty is a universal part of human experience, and that it provokes pleasure in all human. It rivets attention in all of us, and impels actions that help ensure the survival of our genes. Our extreme sensitivity to beauty is hard-wired.” In other there is an instinctive behaviour in every TV viewer, irrespective of gender, to pay some attention to appearance of the presenters.

However, this finding should be taken on a face value because while it is confirmed in this section that both genders pay almost equal attention to appearance, it should not be mistaken to mean that they both have same motivations to observe appearance of TV presenters.

RQ Two: What physical features about the TV presenters do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe?

The findings in Table 2 show that majority (42.3 percent) of the male respondents observe the mannerism of the TV presenters; only 9.9 percent of the male viewers observe the facial appearance of the TV presenters and 19.6% observe their fashion (clothing, hairdo and make-up); whereas with the female TV viewers, majority (45%) observe their fashion (clothing, hairdo and make-up), and a sizable 26.8% of them observe the facial appearance of the TV presenters, and only 11.5% observe their mannerism.

While both men and women seem to always get attracted by appearances of TV presenters, they do not always have the same point of attraction. Male viewers are more concerned about the mannerism of the presenters, whereas the female viewers are more concerned about the clothing, hairdo and make-up of the TV presenters. It goes to buttress what Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) suggested that females learn to be more concerned with the more observable attributes rather than focusing on less or non-observable attributes. That is to say, women tend to judge people mostly by their observable appearances at the expense of other non-observable attributes of a person.

While mannerism might also be an observable feature; clothing, hairdo and make-up of the TV presenters are more manifest features of the presenters. It means that the female viewers are more particular about the more manifest observable physical features of the TV presenters than the men.

RQ Three: What are the attitudes of male and female TV viewers in Owerri towards the physical features of the TV presenters?

The findings in Table 3 show that majority (31.9%) of the 163 male respondents are critical of the appearances of the TV presenters. Some 20.8% express admiration towards appearance of the TV presenters, 25.2% are indifferent about the appearances of the presenters. It is a different path for the female TV viewers, majority (47.1%) of whom express admiration towards appearance of

the TV presenters, 25.1% are critical of the appearances, and only 15.7% are indifferent about the appearances.

Most times, male TV viewers' attention to the presenters' appearance is to criticize the appearances of the presenters or they are just indifferent about the appearances of the presenters; whereas female TV viewers' attention to the presenters' appearance is mostly to admire the appearance of the TV presenters and sometimes express some criticism toward the appearances. What is clear here is that attitudes of male and female TV viewers in Owerri towards the physical features of the TV presenters are way different.

RQ Four: Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to observe the appearances of female TV presenters more than male TV presenters?

The findings in Table 4 show that majority (66.3%) of the male TV viewers tend to observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters; in the same vein, majority (70.7%) of the female TV viewers tend to observe the appearance of female TV presenters more than the male TV presenters.

That is to say, female TV presenters are the ones whose appearances are largely checked out by the TV viewers, irrespective of the gender of the viewer. Little wonder Fox (1997) said that women tend to be mostly defined by their appearances.

Fredrickson and Roberts (1997) also asserted that women are mostly victims of lookism because of the proclivity for people to describe them in terms of what they look like and boys in terms of what they do. Therefore, Daubney's (2015, p. 2) assertion that it is "no longer clear who is a victim of appearance stereotypes and who is obsessional with appearance," goes contrary to our findings. Women are mostly the *victims* of lookism.

RQ Five: Do male and female TV viewers in Owerri tend to pay more attention to the appearances of TV presenters than their presentations?

The findings in Table 5 show that majority (74.2%) of the male TV viewers have no tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations; and same goes to the female TV viewers: majority (50.3%) have no tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations. only 7.9% of the females have a recurring tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations and 29.8% have an occasional tendency to observe the appearances of TV presenters more than their presentations.

Male and female TV viewers pay varying attention to the appearances of TV presenters but the presentations of the TV presenters still take much of their time.

CONCLUSION/RECOMMENDATIONS

Both male and female TV viewers seem to always get attracted by appearance. It shows that gender is not at a factor in determining who takes note of the appearances of the TV presenters.

But male and female TV viewers do not have same motivations to observe appearance of TV presenters: Female viewers are more particular about the manifest observable physical features of the TV presenters like their clothing and hair style than the men.

There is also a divergence between the attitude of male and female TV viewers in Owerri towards the physical features of the TV presenters, as female TV viewers' attention to the presenters' appearance is mostly to admire the appearance of the TV presenters while men show more critical stance towards the appearances of the TV presenters.

However it is the women who are mostly the *victims* of lookism in the broadcast media. Most of the TV viewers tend to observe the appearance of female TV presenters. Therefore, while attention to appearance is a universal issue, motivation to pay attention to appearance and attitude towards attention is gender-specific. Moreover, as women suffer lookism more in TV presentation, it is safe to conclude that lookism in TV is a gender specific concern.

It is on that basis we suggest the following recommendation:

TV producers should ensure they keep the hairdo, clothing and make-up of the female presenters as moderate as possible to avoid warranting undue attention on the presenters.

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